

22IEM06 S-CALe Up

D5 Report on UV stability of chipSCALe photodiodes down to 300 nm

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Glossary

C-V	Capacitance - Voltage
FZ	Float Zone
IQD	Internal Quantum Deficiency
I-V	Current - Voltage
LED	Light emitting diode
MIS	Metal-insulator-semiconductor
NIR	Near infrared
PECVD	Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition
PL	Photoluminescence
PQED	Predictable quantum efficient detector
PUD	Photodiode under test
QSSPC	Quasi-Steady-State Photoconductance
SRV	Surface Recombination Velocity
UV	Ultraviolet
VIS	Visible

Notification about UV-dose:

In this publication, the term "dose" refers to the physical quantity "radiant exposure" (in J/cm²), which describes the received energy per area.

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1 Introduction

Spectral response of detectors from 300 nm to 1000 nm is a key quantity within Photometry and Radiometry and is the basis for the traceability of other quantities within the spectral range as well. It is well known that UV radiation deteriorate detectors and causing them to drift. The aim of this task is to evaluate the stability against UV exposure of the photodiodes developed in the 18SIB10 chipS-CALe project. To this end, irradiation studies both on passivated test samples and actual photodiodes were performed to link the radiation damage on test samples to degradation in responsivity of photodiodes via simulations. The minority carrier lifetime and fixed dielectric charge of the passivated test samples before and after UV-irradiation were measured, the surface recombination velocity was extracted by 2D simulation, and subsequently, the degradation in responsivity of the photodiodes fabricated with such passivation due to UV-exposure were estimated by 3D simulations. The actual photodiodes produced in the 18SIB10 chipS-CALe project were irradiated with UV radiation, the change in response was tested and compared with the predictions of simulations to validate the simulation models.

2 Test samples and photodiodes used in the UV stability study

2.1 Test samples for lifetime analysis

The lifetime measurements were carried out on double-side-polished, high resistivity, p-type, 500 μm thick, float zone (FZ) silicon wafers passivated identically on both sides. Such wafers have a long bulk lifetime (>10 ms), ensuring that the measured effective minority carrier lifetime is dominated by surface recombination. The process established in the chipS-CALe project was adopted, i.e. a 6 nm thick thermal oxide was formed at the wafer surface and subsequently capped by a ~ 65 nm thick SiNx layer using plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD).

2.2 Test samples for characterization of fixed charge density

The fixed charge density was determined by Capacitance-Voltage (C-V) measurements on metal-insulator-semiconductor (MIS) structures made on high resistivity, p-type, FZ crystalline silicon wafers, which were laser cut into 40 x 40 mm² samples. The MIS structures were fabricated by thermal evaporation of Al contacts on the front and rear of the sample. The rear contact covers the whole back surface (which had been boron implanted, to ensure ohmic contact to the lowly doped substrate), whereas a shadow mask was used on the front side to form 48 circular MIS capacitors of three different sizes ($\varnothing = 1$ mm, 2 mm, and 3 mm), as illustrated in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1. (Left) Layout of Al contact pads on the C-V sample. The area of the sample that is exposed with ultra-violet radiation is indicated by the light blue color. (Right) Photograph of a C-V sample with front Al contact pads.

2.3 Photodiodes

Photodiodes manufactured in the chipS.CALe project were packaged by USN, placed in housings by PTB and sent to partners who carried out the UV irradiation and responsivity measurements. Photodiodes of size 11 mm x 11 mm were used in this study. The photodiodes are p-type and passivated with a stack of 6 nm thermal SiO₂ and PECVD SiN_x as the test samples.

3 UV irradiation

3.1 Irradiation at RISE

The photodiodes and silicon test samples were exposed to UV radiation of three wavelengths from different UV sources: 222 nm (excimer lamp), 279 nm (LED), and 300 nm (LED). The spectra of the UV sources are shown in Figure 3.1. Different optical setups were used for the various UV sources due to their physical nature and their varying divergence. For exposure at 222 nm, the excimer lamp was placed inside a black box, radiating upwards through an aperture in the box. A cylinder, internally covered with black aluminium foil, standing on the box was used to keep the sample at a fixed distance above the aperture. The irradiance and dose distribution on the sample was controlled by adjusting the size of the aperture in the box and the height of the cylinder holding the sample. For exposure of the photodiodes at 279 nm and 300 nm and the test samples at 279 nm, the UV radiation from the LEDs was focused using a lens (50 mm focal length) and projected onto the sample. The exposed area and the dose profile was controlled by adjusting the position of the lens and the sample relative to the LED. For exposure of the silicon test samples at 300 nm, a conical beam guide internally covered with reflective aluminium was used instead of the focusing lens to collect the UV radiation onto the sample, due to the lower intensity of the 300 nm LED.

Figure 3.1. Top: photograph of the UV sources. From left to right: 222 nm excimer lamp, 279 nm LED, 300 nm LED. Bottom: Emission spectrum of the UV sources at 222 nm, 279 nm, and 300 nm.

The silicon test samples (size 40 mm x 40 mm) were positioned in a 3D-printed holder with a 20 mm circular aperture centred on the sample, see example in Figure 3.2. For the photodiodes, a 4x4 mm² mask was placed in front of the photodiode housing, enabling selective exposure of one quadrant of the 11x11 mm² photodiode area, see Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2. Left: photograph of 3D printed holder for silicon test sample. Right: Photograph of the 4x4 mm² mask in front of a photodiode housing. The UV radiation is passing through the mask and is projected onto one of the quadrants drawn on the photodiode housing cover. Note: during the UV exposure, the cover was removed, and the mask was positioned close to the photodiode housing.

3.2 Irradiation at SFI Davos

For the irradiation process, the active surface of the photodiode (11 mm²) was divided into four quadrants, each designated for exposure to different doses (10 J/cm², 25 J/cm², 50 J/cm², and 100 J/cm²). These quadrants were separated by 1 mm gaps from each other and from the edge of the active area, ensuring clear distinction during subsequent responsivity measurements (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3. Delimitation of photodiode's active area into four quadrants, each designated for exposure to different doses.

The irradiations were carried out using a Helium Cadmium (HeCd) laser emitting at 325 nm. Micro-optics were employed to reshape and expand the Gaussian-profiled 1 mm laser spot into a uniform 6x6 mm² beam. A 3D-printed mask was then attached to the photodiode housing to trim the beam down to 4x4 mm² and accurately position it on the intended quadrant of the photodiode surface (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4. Example of printed mask application on the photodiode housing.

During the UV irradiation, the beam's irradiance was kept constant (omitting the laser's nominal instability of approximately $\pm 2\%$). The different doses were achieved by varying the exposure time to the 325 nm UV light. Each quadrant was irradiated separately, subsequently in increasing order of dose. The beam properties and exposure times to attain different doses are listed in table 3.1.

Table 3.1. 325 nm UV irradiation beam properties and dose determinations.

Parameter	Value
UV beam size (total)	6x6 mm ²
UV quadrant size (masked)	<u>4x4 mm²</u>
PQED area	20.0065 mm ²
Mode	Continuous
Irradiance (Measured with PQED)	<u>207 W/m² (20.7 mW/cm²)</u>
UV duration for 10 J/cm ²	<u>483 s (8 min)</u>
UV duration for 25 J/cm ²	<u>1208 s (20 min)</u>
UV duration for 50 J/cm ²	<u>2415 s (40 min)</u>
UV duration for 100 J/cm ²	<u>4830 s (80.5 min)</u>

4 Measurements of photodiode responsivity as a function of UV exposure - I (RISE and SFI Davos)

4.1 Results from RISE

The effect of UV exposure of the photodiodes was evaluated both by monitoring the photodiode signal during the exposure, and by measuring the responsivity of the photodiode before and after UV exposure.

During exposure with 222 nm and 279 nm, the photodiode signal at first stays constant until there is a significant decrease in the signal, and thereafter it stabilizes at a lower level, see Figure 4.1 and 4.2. This shows that there is a certain threshold dose of UV radiation that causes degradation of the photodiode. For 222 nm, the threshold dose is approximately 0,005 J/cm², while it is approximately 0,6 J/cm² for 279 nm. The threshold dose appears to be independent of irradiance intensity, as seen in Figure 4.2, where the threshold was reached at approximately the same received dose (in J/cm²) but where the irradiance (in J/s/cm²) in the top graph was a factor of ~20 higher than in the lower graph.

The time trace of the photodiode signal during exposure correlates with a decrease in photodiode responsivity. The upper panel in Figure 4.3 shows the time trace of the photodiode signal, overlaid with vertical lines that indicates at which times when the exposure was paused and the responsivity of the same photodiode was measured. The responsivity was measured using a beam size of approximately 1 mm, scanning over both the exposed and unexposed area of the photodiode. As seen in the lower panel in Figure 4.3, the responsivity in the exposed area decreases with higher UV dose, following the same behaviour as the photodiode signal in the upper panel.

For exposure with the 300 nm LED, no decrease in the photodiode signal could be observed up to the dose of 100 J/cm², where the experiment was stopped. No decrease in responsivity could be observed caused by this exposure, as seen in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.1. Photodiode signal during exposure at 200 nm, irradiance 0,20 mW/cm², photodiode bias 5V.

Figure 4.2. Photodiode signal during exposure at 279 nm, irradiance 4,18 mW/cm² (top) and 0,21 mW/cm² (bottom), photodiode bias 5V.

Figure 4.3. Top: Photodiode signal during exposure at 279 nm, irradiance 1,1 mW/cm², photodiode bias 5V. Bottom: relative responsivity measured scanning across the photodiode surface, measured at time points indicated in the top figure (measured with 5 V bias using a 279 nm beam of size ~1 mm, 0,10 mW/cm²).

Figure 4.4. Relative responsivity of a photodiode after various doses of 300 nm exposure, scanned over both exposed (gray) and non-exposed (white) area of the photodiode.

The observed threshold doses for the three different wavelengths are summarized in Table 4.1. Though, it should be noted that the exact wavelength dependence of the threshold dose cannot be concluded from this experiment. This is because the UV sources does not emit one single wavelength but have a non-finite spectral width. Because the 300 nm LED spectrum has a tail stretching down to ~280 nm, and exposure with this LED do not lead to any decrease in responsivity, it is likely that it is mainly the high energy part of the 279 nm LED spectrum that is responsible for the degradation caused by exposure to the radiation from this LED.

Table 4.1. Threshold dose for each wavelength.

Wavelength (nm)	Threshold dose (J/cm ²)
222	0,005
279	0,6
300	>100

The decrease in relative responsivity of a photodiode UV exposed beyond the threshold dose depends on the intensity and wavelength of the probe beam, as can be seen in Figure 4.5. A lower intensity of the probe beam gives a smaller decrease in relative responsivity in the exposed area compared to a higher intensity. In other words, the photodiode's response to irradiation is no longer linear after UV exposure beyond the threshold dose. The wavelength dependence of the decrease in responsivity can also be seen in Figure 4.6. This figure also shows that performing the measurement of responsivity with or without an applied bias voltage over the photodiode does not affect the conclusion about lowered responsivity for the UV exposed photodiode.

Figure 4.5. Relative responsivity scanned over photodiode surface with prob beam of various intensities. The gray marked area has been exposed to 279 nm UV radiation, >0,6 J/cm². Responsivity measured using 280 nm beam (upper panel) and 405 nm beam (lower graph) with diameter approximately 1,5 mm.

Figure 4.6. Ratio between measured responsivity before and after UV exposure (222 nm, 0,6 J/cm²). Responsivity measured with and without applied bias voltage. Left: Measured with UV set-up. Right: Measured with VIS/NIR set-up. The difference in responsivity ratio in the overlapping region 350-500 nm is assigned to the difference in intensity of the probe beam in the UV-setup and the VIS/NIR setup.

A test with annealing of a UV degraded photodiode at 100°C for three hours showed that annealing at this condition did not recover the photodiode.

Conclusions:

- UV radiation with wavelengths <300 nm degrades the photodiode.
- There is threshold dose for the UV degradation that depends on the wavelength of the exposure UV radiation.
- The threshold dose does not depend on the UV irradiation intensity.
- After UV exposure beyond the threshold dose, the decrease in photodiode responsivity depends on the intensity and wavelength of the probe beam.

4.2 Results from SFI Davos

To evaluate potential degradation of the active surface during UV exposure in real time, the photodiode's photocurrent was monitored using a high-precision electrometer. As shown in Figure 4.7, no noticeable behaviour or signs of deterioration were detected during exposure at any dose. The observed variations, all <2%, are likely attributable to the HeCd laser's nominal instability.

Figure 4.7. Real-time measurements of diodes photocurrent during its exposure to 325nm UV irradiation.

A stable 473 nm laser beam with low uncertainty (<0.1%) was used to measure the 2D responsivity of the photodiode before and after irradiation. For higher resolution scans, the laser spot was reduced to 0.66x0.64 mm². Measurements were conducted at three different laser powers: 1 mW, 0.5 μW, and 0.05 μW for each dose.

As shown in Figure 4.8 below, no significant changes were observed in the 2D responsivity tests at 1 mW of 473 nm after UV exposure at varying doses.

Figure 4.8. 2D responsivity measurements results before (top) and after irradiation at different doses. Responsivity measured with a 473 nm stable beam set at 1 mW.

Further 2D responsivity tests conducted at 0.5 μ W and 0.05 μ W did not reveal any apparent patterns due to degradation to the UV exposure, as shown in Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9. 2D responsivity measurements results before and after irradiation at different doses. Responsivity measured with a 473 nm stable beam set at 0.5 μ W.

Additionally, to inspect potential responsivity changes in the UV region, a 2D responsivity scan was also performed using the 325 nm laser (0.5 mm² beam spot). As with the 473 nm tests, no significant changes in responsivity were detected after exposure to UV at different doses, as shown in Figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10. 2D responsivity measurements results before and after irradiation at different doses. Responsivity measured with a 325 nm UV beam set at 20 μ W.

Conclusions:

- The sample chipS-CALe C1 photodiode was subjected to UV irradiation at 325 nm, with responsivity studies conducted at both 473 nm (visible) and 325 nm (UV).
- The active area was delimited into four quadrants, each exposed to a specific UV dose (10 J/cm², 25 J/cm², 50 J/cm², 100 J/cm²).
- Real-time monitoring of the chipS-CALe C1 photocurrent during UV exposure at different doses showed no signs of degradation. The slight variations in photocurrent remained within the range of the HeCd laser's stability (2%) irrespective of the dose.
- 2D responsivity tests were conducted before and after UV exposure at 473 nm (using 1 mW, 0.5 μW, and 0.05 μW laser powers) and at 325 nm (50 μW).
- No deterioration or apparent pattern emerged from the 2D responsivity measurements after UV exposure at different doses.
- In conclusion, no signs of degradation were observed in the chipS-CALe photodiode after exposure to 325 nm UV radiation.

5 Measurements of photodiode responsivity as a function of UV exposure - II (PTB)

5.1 Design of the investigation

The PTB investigated the change in spectral responsivity by measuring the photocurrent ratio of the photodiode under test (PUD) and a reference detector before and after UV exposure and comparing the two ratios. PTB has set up six detectors with photodiodes from the previous 18SIB10 chipS-CALe project. The photodiodes under test have a square sensitive area of 11 mm x 11 mm. On each photodiode, four square subareas of 4 mm x 4 mm were identified for the UV exposure. These four squares are separated from each other and from the edge of the sensitive area by 1 mm, as shown in figure 5.1.

A particular square subarea y ($y = 2, 3, 4, 5$) on photodiode C_x ($x = 5, 6, 8, 10, 11, 12$) is called C_x-y . For example, C5-2 refers to the 4 mm x 4 mm square at position 2 of photodiode C5. During the measurement of the photocurrent ratio, each of the 4 mm x 4 mm squares was irradiated within a circular spot with a diameter of about 3.1 mm. The circular spots were centered to the squares, as shown in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1. Square sensitive area of 11 mm x 11 mm of a photodiode under test (dark gray) with four 4 mm x 4 mm square subareas **2**, **3**, **4**, and **5** indicated by squares in red, orange, green and blue, respectively, and identified for UV exposure. The positions of the measurement spots are indicated by light gray circles.

The reference detectors are 3-element reflection trap detectors equipped with windowless silicon photodiodes of type Hamamatsu S1337-1010 or S5227-1010 for the wavelength range from 280 nm to 405 nm and of type Hamamatsu S3411 and S6337 for the wavelength range from 395 nm to 1000 nm.

The exposure to UV radiation was carried out by RISE as described in section 3. Table 5.1 shows the UV exposure levels of the 24 subareas of the 6 photodiodes under test. Two photodiodes have been irradiated at a wavelength of 300 nm with exposure levels ranging from 0 J/cm² to 100 J/cm². Another two photodiodes have been irradiated at a wavelength of 280 nm with exposure levels ranging from 0 J/cm² to 10 J/cm². The last two photodiodes have not been irradiated in the UV except during the measurement.

When irradiating the four subareas of a PUD with very different exposure levels, it is assumed that the exposure to UV radiation of one subarea does not change the properties of the photodiode in the other three subareas.

The total exposure during the measurement in the wavelength range from 280 nm to 405 nm is below 0.002 J/cm².

Table 5.1. UV exposure of the photodiodes under test. C6-3 and C6-5 should not be irradiated in the UV, however, have been irradiated unintendedly (*).

Photodiode	Subarea	Wavelength of exposure	Exposure
C5	C5-2	-	0 J/cm ²
	C5-3		0 J/cm ²
	C5-4		0 J/cm ²
	C5-5		0 J/cm ²

C6	C6-2	300 nm	10 J/cm ²
	C6-3		1 J/cm ² (*)
	C6-4		100 J/cm ²
	C6-5		1 J/cm ² (*)
C8	C8-2	280 nm	0.5 J/cm ²
	C8-3		0 J/cm ²
	C8-4		10 J/cm ²
	C8-5		10 J/cm ²
C10	C10-2	-	0 J/cm ²
	C10-3		0 J/cm ²
	C10-4		0 J/cm ²
	C10-5		0 J/cm ²
C11	C11-2	300 nm	10 J/cm ²
	C11-3		0 J/cm ²
	C11-4		100 J/cm ²
	C11-5		0 J/cm ²
C12	C12-2	280 nm	0.5 J/cm ²
	C12-3		0 J/cm ²
	C12-4		0.5 J/cm ²
	C12-5		10 J/cm ²

The measurements were carried out in a calibration facility mainly used to determine the spectral responsivity by comparing the photocurrent of the device to be calibrated and reference detectors whose spectral responsivity had been previously calibrated against cryogenic electrical substitution radiometers. The calibration facility consists of radiation sources, a double grating monochromator with order-sorting filters and a detector positioning system. The radiation sources are a xenon short-arc lamp for wavelengths ≤ 405 nm and a tungsten-filament halogen bulb lamp for wavelengths ≥ 395 nm. The detectors were measured under two orientations, i.e. 0° and 90° , with respect to rotation around the axis of the incoming radiation. The PUDs were measured without bias voltage and with reverse bias voltage of 1 V and 5 V for wavelengths ≤ 405 nm and ≥ 395 nm, respectively.

The measurements have been analyzed by calculating the Ratio R of the photocurrent of the PUD I_{PUD} and that of the reference detector I_{ref} which is equal to the ratio of the spectral responsivity of the two detectors s_{PUD} and s_{ref} , respectively

$$R = I_{\text{PUD}}/I_{\text{ref}} = s_{\text{PUD}}/s_{\text{ref}} \quad (5.1)$$

The ratio of the photocurrent ratio after and before UV exposure is then

$$R^{\text{after}}/R^{\text{before}} = \frac{s_{\text{PUD}}^{\text{after}}}{s_{\text{PUD}}^{\text{before}}} / \frac{s_{\text{ref}}^{\text{after}}}{s_{\text{ref}}^{\text{before}}} \quad (5.2)$$

with superscripts «before» and «after» indicating the quantities before and after UV exposure, respectively. It is

$$\frac{s_{\text{ref}}^{\text{after}}}{s_{\text{ref}}^{\text{before}}} = 1 + \Delta_{\text{ref}}(t^{\text{after}} - t^{\text{before}}) \quad (5.3)$$

describing the temporal change of the spectral responsivity being linear with time. t^{after} and t^{before} are the time of the measurements after and before the UV exposure.

$$\Delta_{\text{ref}} = \frac{1}{s_{\text{ref}}} \frac{ds_{\text{ref}}}{dt} \quad (5.4)$$

is the relative change of the spectral responsivity of the reference detector over time, which has been studied over more than 10 years and is precisely known. Combining equ. 5.2 and 5.3 gives the ratio of the spectral responsivity after to before UV exposure of the PUD which is a measure of the stability of the PUD against UV exposure.

$$s_{\text{PUD}}^{\text{after}}/s_{\text{PUD}}^{\text{before}} = \frac{R^{\text{after}}}{R^{\text{before}}} \left(1 + \Delta_{\text{ref}}(t^{\text{after}} - t^{\text{before}}) \right) \quad (5.5)$$

The time difference ($t^{\text{after}} - t^{\text{before}}$) between the time of the measurements after and before the UV exposure is about 4 months.

5.2 Experimental results

The experimental results are shown here as the ratio of the spectral responsivity after to before UV exposure calculated according to equation (5.5) for each subarea of a PUD. It is abbreviated in the following as **after-to-before responsivity ratio**.

The following figures show, in addition to the subareas of a PUD, the second reference detectors T8 and t52-1 used in the respective spectral range. The measurement data from these reference detectors were analyzed in the same way as the data from the subareas of the PUDs to show that the measurement conditions were stable. The measurements with the xenon lamp and with the tungsten halogen lamp as radiation source were carried out separately. Therefore, the experimental results are also presented separately.

5.2.1 Photodiodes not exposed to UV radiation

The photodiodes C5 and C10 were not exposed to UV radiation. Figure 5.2 shows the after-to-before responsivity ratio for the subareas of C5 and wavelengths ≥ 395 nm and for a bias voltage of 5 V (left) and 0 V(right). The increase of the ratio at long wavelengths is not understood. It is thought to be due to too low bias voltage, as the increase at zero bias is about three times that at 5 V. Figure 5.3 shows the after-to-before responsivity ratio for C10 and wavelengths ≥ 395 nm and for a bias voltage of 5 V. The offset of C10-3 is caused by a small dust particle in the corresponding subarea. Figure 5.4 shows the after-to-before responsivity ratio for C5 (left) and C10 (right), wavelengths ≤ 405 nm and a bias voltage of 1 V. Again, a small offset of C10-3 of about 0.0005, caused by a small dust particle, is visible.

The after-to-before responsivity ratio being 1 ± 0.0005 indicates that the spectral responsivity in the subareas of PUD C5 and C10, which have not been exposed to UV radiation, is stable within ± 0.05 % over the period of about 4 months from the measurements before UV exposure to those after UV exposure.

Figure 5.2. After-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≥ 395 nm for all four subareas of PUD C5 which was not exposed to UV radiation. The left figure and the right one show the ratio for a bias voltage of 5 V and 0 V, respectively. The orientation is 0° .

Figure 5.3. After-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≥ 395 nm of the irradiated PUDs for all four subareas of PUD C10 which was not exposed to UV radiation. The offset of C10-3 is caused by a small dust particle in the corresponding subarea. The bias voltage is 5 V and the orientation is 0° .

Figure 5.4. After-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≤ 405 nm for all four subareas of PUD C5 (left) and C10 (right) which were not exposed to UV radiation. The offset of C10-3 is caused by a small dust particle in the corresponding subarea. The bias voltage is 1 V. The results shown are the average over both orientations 0° and 90° .

5.2.2 Photodiodes exposed to UV radiation at wavelength of 300 nm

The photodiodes C6 and C11 were exposed to UV radiation at the wavelength 300 nm and with exposure levels of 1 J/cm^2 , 10 J/cm^2 and 100 J/cm^2 . Fig. 5.5 shows that the after-to-before responsivity ratio of irradiated and non-irradiated subareas of these PUDs is very similar to each other and those of the non-irradiated PUDs C5 and C10 (see left side of Fig. 5.2 and Fig. 5.3) indicating that the spectral responsivity is not changed in the wavelength range from 395 nm to 1005 nm.

Fig. 5.6 shows the after-to-before responsivity ratio of all subareas of C6 and C11. Only for the non-irradiated subareas C11-3 and C11-5, the after-to-before responsivity ratio is equal to 1 ± 0.0005 indicating that the spectral responsivity in these subareas is stable within $\pm 0.05\%$. All other subareas of these PUDs show an after-to-before responsivity ratio that deviates from 1 by up to 0.0035 indicating a change of the spectral responsivity of up to 0.35%. However, in the wavelength range from 300 nm to 405 nm, the spectral responsivity is stable within a band of $\pm 0.25\%$ even for a UV exposure of up to 100 J/cm^2 at a wavelength of 300 nm.

Figure 5.5. After-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≥ 395 nm for all four subareas of PUD C6 (left) and C11 (right) which were exposed to UV radiation at the wavelength 300 nm and with exposure levels as indicated in the Figures. The bias voltage is 5 V and the orientation is 0° .

Figure 5.6. After-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≤ 405 nm for all four subareas of PUD C6 (left) and C11 (right) which were exposed to UV radiation at the wavelength 300 nm and with exposure levels as indicated in the Figures. The bias voltage is 1 V. The results shown are the average over both orientations 0° and 90° .

5.2.3 Photodiodes exposed to UV radiation at wavelength of 280 nm

The photodiodes C8 and C12 were exposed to UV radiation at the wavelength 280 nm and with exposure levels of 0.5 J/cm² and 10 J/cm².

Fig. 5.7 shows the after-to-before responsivity ratio of all subareas of C12. The after-to-before responsivity ratio of the non-irradiated subarea C12-3 and of the subarea irradiated with an exposure of 0.5 J/cm² (C12-2 and C12-4) are very similar to each other and those of the non-irradiated PUDs C5 and C10 (see left side of Fig. 5.2 and Fig. 5.3) indicating that the spectral responsivity is stable within a band of ±0.05 % in the wavelength range from 395 nm to 1005 nm.

The after-to-before responsivity ratio of the subarea C12-5 irradiated with an exposure of 10 J/cm² is reduced to values ranging from 0.3 to 0.9 which indicates that the spectral responsivity is drastically reduced to values ranging from 30 % to 90 % of its original value. The comparison of the after-to-before responsivity ratio and the power of the radiation used for the measurements suggests that the after-to-before responsivity ratio of subarea C12-5 strongly depends on this power. This is confirmed by further investigations.

Figure 5.8 shows the after-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≤ 405 nm for all four subareas of PUD C12. The spectral responsivity of the non-irradiated subarea C12-3 is stable within ±0.05 %. The after-to-before responsivity ratio of the subareas C12-2 and C12-4 irradiated with an exposure of 0.5 J/cm² are similar to those of the subareas of C6 and C11 irradiated at a wavelength of 300 nm (see Fig. 5.6) and indicate that the spectral responsivity of C12-2 and C12-4 had not changed by more than 0.25% at wavelengths ≤ 405 nm. The after-to-before responsivity ratio of the subarea C12-5 irradiated with an exposure of 10 J/cm² is reduced to values ranging from 0.3 to 0.6 which indicates that the spectral responsivity is drastically reduced to values ranging from 30 % to 60 % of its original value.

Figure 5.7. After-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≥ 395 nm for all four subareas of PUD C12 which were exposed to UV radiation at the wavelength 280 nm and with exposure levels as indicated in the Figures. The left and the right figure show the ratio in the range from 0.999 to 1.007 and from 0 to 1.1, respectively. The bias voltage is 5 V and the orientation is 0°. The right figure shows in addition the power P of the radiation used to measure the photocurrent ratio of PUD to reference detector (see section 5.1).

Figure 5.8. After-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≤ 405 nm for all four subareas of PUD C12 which were exposed to UV radiation at the wavelength 280 nm and with exposure levels as indicated in the Figures. The bias voltage is 1 V. The results shown are the average over both orientations 0° and 90° . The left and the right figure show the ratio in the range from 0.997 to 1.004 and from 0 to 1.1, respectively.

Figure 5.9 shows the after-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≥ 395 nm of the subareas C8-2 and C8-3 which were exposed to UV radiation at the wavelength 280 nm and with exposure levels of 0.5 J/cm^2 and 0 J/cm^2 , respectively. The fiber had been removed, and the measurement had been repeated. The results for the wavelengths ≥ 395 nm are shown in fig. 5.10. The remaining deviation of the after-to-before responsivity ratio of C8-2 and C8-3 from 1 in the wavelength range from 395 nm to 600 nm is probably caused by contamination of the photodiode surface during removal of the small fiber.

Figure 5.9. After-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≥ 395 nm for the subareas C8-2 and C8-3 of PUD C8 which were exposed to UV radiation at the wavelength 280 nm and with exposure levels as indicated in the Figures. The bias voltage is 5 V and the orientation is 0° . The offset of the ratio for C8-2 is caused by a small fiber which shades a small part of the sensitive area.

Figure 5.10. After-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≥ 395 nm for all four subareas of PUD C12 which were exposed to UV radiation at the wavelength 280 nm and with exposure levels as indicated in the Figures. The left and the right figure show the ratio in the range from 0.999 to 1.007 and from 0 to 1.1, respectively. The bias voltage is 5 V and the orientation is 0° . The right figure shows in addition the power P of the radiation used to measure the photocurrent ratio of PUD to reference detector (see section 5.1). The results shown in this figure were obtained after removal of a small fiber shading subarea C8-2.

Figure 5.11. After-to-before responsivity ratio at wavelengths ≤ 405 nm for all four subareas of PUD C8 which were exposed to UV radiation at the wavelength 280 nm and with exposure levels as indicated in the Figures. The bias voltage is 1 V. The results shown are the average over both orientations 0° and 90° . The left and the right figure show the ratio in the range from 0.997 to 1.004 and from 0 to 1.1, respectively. The results shown in this figure were obtained after removal of a small fiber shading subarea C8-2.

The results obtained for C8 are similar to those obtained for C12: The spectral responsivity of C8-3 is not changed due to the exposure of 0.5 J/cm^2 at a wavelength of 280 nm but is probably slightly changed by up to 0.15 % by contamination of the photodiode surface during removal of a small fiber. The exposure of 10 J/cm^2 at a wavelength of 280 nm leads to a dramatic reduction of the spectral responsivity down to values ranging from 15 % to 80 % of its original value. At the exposure level of 10 J/cm^2 , the after-to-before responsivity ratio and the reduction in spectral responsivity appear to be strongly dependent on the power of the radiation used for the measurements.

5.3 Conclusions on changes in spectral responsivity due to UV exposure

PTB and RISE investigated the change in spectral responsivity of photodiodes from the previous 18SIB10 chipS:CALe project due to UV exposure. The spectral responsivity of these photodiodes in the wavelength range from 300 nm to 1005 nm does not change by more than 0.25 % when irradiated at a wavelength of 300 nm with an exposure of up to 100 J/cm^2 or at a wavelength of 280 nm with an exposure of up to 0.5 J/cm^2 . These photodiodes can therefore be considered stable in the 300nm to 1005nm wavelength range for many applications.

6 Experimental results from UV exposure of test samples and simulations

6.1 Lifetime and fixed charge measurements as a function of UV irradiation

A BT Imaging LIS-R1 unit with an excitation wavelength of 808 nm was used for recording photoluminescence (PL) images of the test samples before and after irradiation with UV light. The PL intensity was calibrated to the effective minority carrier lifetime based on a QSSPC measurement carried out in the central region of the wafer. The images were primarily used to check that the samples had been correctly exposed to UV light. The lifetime variation that is observed in the PL images for each sample (Figure 6.1) corresponds well with the UV dose that each sample was exposed to.

For measurement of injection-dependent lifetime curves, the quasi-steady-state photoconductance (QSSPC) method was adopted, using a Sinton WCT-120TS lifetime tester. With this setup, the excess carrier density is calculated from the conductivity of the passivated silicon wafer under illumination, as measured by an inductively coupled coil. Each sample was precisely centered on top of the coil, which has a diameter of 19 mm. The effective minority carrier lifetime (t_{eff}) was defined at an injection level $Dn = 1e15 \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

BEFORE UV EXPOSURE

AFTER UV EXPOSURE

Wafer 115

Wafer 152

Wafer 210

Figure 6.1. PL images of laser cut samples before and after UV exposure. The color bar indicates the minority carrier lifetime in μs .

The C-V measurements were carried out using a Keithley 4200 Semiconductor Characterization System. Based on the measured C-V curves, the parameters of interest including dielectric thickness (t_d), flat-band voltage (V_{fb}), and fixed charge density (Q_f) were estimated. For improving the accuracy of the results, the measurements were done at low frequencies (1 kHz), making sure that the measured C_{acc} is reasonably close to C_d which can be calculated by obtaining the dielectric thickness and permittivity from ellipsometry measurements. Hysteresis measurements were also done to make sure that the measured charge is primarily due to fixed charges and that the mobile charge contribution is negligible.

The results of the C-V and lifetime measurements are summarized in Table 6.1. UV irradiation of the samples results in a reduction in the effective minority carrier lifetime, i.e., for increasing photon energy, a lower dose is required to degrade the surface passivation. Exposure of the samples to UV reduces the effective minority carrier lifetime by up to 70 %. The initial effective minority carrier lifetime for these sample was measured at approximately 10 ms. Moreover, the fixed charge density is reduced with up to one order of magnitude (from $\sim 2.5e+12$ to $\sim 2.8e+12 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) when the surface is exposed to UV irradiation. The reduction in the fixed charge density corresponds well with the reduction in the effective minority carrier lifetime, i.e., both decreases in proportion to the UV exposure.

Table 6.1 Summary of C-V and lifetime measurements for exposure to three different UV wavelengths.

C-V sample	Lifetime sample	UV wavel. (nm)	UV Dose (J/cm ²)	Q _f	t _{eff} reduction
021-A	115-A	0	No	2.50E+12	0-10 % (reference)
021-B	-	300	1	-	Not analyzed
021-C	-	300	1	1.39E+12	Not analyzed
021-D	210-B	300	10	-	15.4 %
021-E	210-C	300	10	8.00E+11	25.5 %
021-F	210-D	300	100	-	20.0 %
021-G	210-F	300	100	7.00E+11	25.4 %
133-B	152-A	279	0.1	1.23E+12	13.2 %
133-C	152-B	279	0.1	-	19.4 %
133-D	152-C	279	1	-	65.5 %
133-E	152-D	279	1	2.80E+11	59.5 %
133-F	152-E	279	10	-	49.8 %
133-G	152-G	279	10	2.80E+11	51.2 %
183-B	284-B	222	0.001	1.60E+12	7.0 %
183-C	284-C	222	0.001	-	2.0 %
183-D	284-D	222	0.01	-	71.1 %
183-E	284-F	222	0.01	3.10E+11	69.0 %
183-F	115-F	222	0.1	-	63.7 %
183-G	284-G	222	0.1	2.90E+11	68.8 %

6.2 Simulations of SRV and IQD as a function of UV irradiation

6.2.1 Methodology of extraction of SRV and bulk lifetime by fitting simulation with lifetime measurement data

Figure 6.2 illustrates simulation structure before UV exposure (a) and after UV exposure (b). The simulation structure includes a Silicon wafer with SiO₂/SiN_x layers on both sides. The whole structure is illuminated with light source at 808 nm.

Before UV exposure, the relation between effective lifetime τ_{eff} and bulk lifetime τ_{bulk} can be described by:

$$1/\tau_{eff} = 1/\tau_{bulk} + 2S_{eff-bef}/W \quad (6.1)$$

Where $S_{eff-bef}$ is the surface recombination rate before UV exposure and W is the wafer thickness. The surface recombination rate S_{eff} changes after UV exposure. Since only one side of the samples were exposed to UV light, the effective lifetime after UV exposure is calculated by:

$$1/\tau_{eff} = 1/\tau_{bulk} + S_{eff-bef}/W + S_{eff-aft}/W \quad (6.2)$$

By changing the surface recombination rate S_{eff} and bulk lifetime τ_{bulk} , the extracted τ_{eff} is fitted with experiment data. Best fit gives true values of S_{eff} and τ_{eff} of the samples.

Figure 6.2 Simulation structure before UV exposure (a) and after UV exposure (b)

6.2.2 Overview of test samples and UV exposure setup

The samples are exposed under UV light at three different wavelengths 222 nm, 279 nm and 300 nm. After exposure, lifetime measurement was performed on the samples. Table 6.2 shows the overview of exposure wavelengths and exposure doses.

Table 6.2 Overview of test samples for lifetime measurement

Sample	UV wavelength (nm)	UV dose (J/cm ²)
210-A (for reference)	N/A	N/A
210-B	300	10
210-C	300	10
210-D	300	100
210-E (for reference)	N/A	N/A
210-F	300	100
152-A	279	0.1
152-B	279	0.1
152-C	279	1
152-D	279	1
152-E	279	10
152-F (for reference)	N/A	N/A
152-G	279	10
284-A (for reference)	N/A	N/A
284-B	222	0.001
284-C	222	0.001
284-D	222	0.01
284-E (for reference)	N/A	N/A
284-F	222	0.01
284-G	222	0.1

6.2.3 Simulation results

Some of the samples in Table 6.2 were selected for extraction of parameters with simulations. Measured fixed charge Q_f in Table 6.1 was used as input for the simulation. The simulation consists of two steps. First, the simulation was fitted with measured data before UV exposure. Good fitting gives the value of $S_{eff-bef}$ in equation (6.1). The second step is the fitting between simulation and measured data after UV exposure. The value of $S_{eff-bef}$ was used for the second fitting based on equation (6.2).

Figure 6.3 plots fitting between simulation and experimental data for the samples that have been exposed at 300 nm with exposure doses of 10 J/cm² and 100 J/cm². Fitting of samples that have been exposed at 279 nm is shown in Figure 6.4. Lower exposure doses of 0.1 J/cm², 1 J/cm² and 10 J/cm² are used at 279 nm wavelength. The simulation is performed for the samples that were exposed at 222 nm at for exposure doses of 0.001 J/cm², 0.01 J/cm² and 0.1 J/cm². The result is plotted in Figure 6.5. In the plots, the curves with solid points show experimental data before UV exposure and the curves with unfilled points show experimental data after UV exposure. Overall, effective lifetime reduces after UV exposure. When the samples are exposure at shorter wavelengths 222 nm and 279 nm, the effective lifetime reduces more although the exposure doses are smaller.

The extracted bulk lifetime and surface recombination of holes/electrons S_{0n}/S_{0p} values before and after UV exposure are summarized in Table 6.3. Bulk lifetime and S_{0n}/S_{0p} do not change much after UV exposure. Fixed charge on the other hand changes inversely proportional to both wavelength and exposure doses.

Figure 6.3 Simulation result of wafer 210-UV exposure at 300 nm

Figure 6.4 Simulation result of wafer 152-UV exposure at 279 nm

Figure 6.5 Simulation result of wafer 284-UV exposure at 222 nm

Table 6.3 Summary of extracted parameters

Wafer	Sample ID	Wave length (nm)	UV dose (J/cm ²)	Fixed charge (cm ⁻²) Measured		Bulk lifetime (ms) Simulated		S _{0n} /S _{0p} (cm/s) Simulated	
				Before	After	Before	After	Before	After
210	210 – B	300	10	2.5x10 ¹²	8x10 ¹¹	5.3	4.9	1300	800
210	210 – F	300	100	2.5x10 ¹²	7x10 ¹¹	5.8	5.3	1500	1000
152	152 – A	279	0.1	2.5x10 ¹²	1.23x10 ¹²	5.7	5.5	650	900
152	152 – C	279	1	2.5x10 ¹²	2.8x10 ¹¹	5.0	3.4	1100	1100
152	152 – G	279	10	2.5x10 ¹²	2.8x10 ¹¹	5.0	4.0	1100	700
284	284 – B	222	0.001	2.5x10 ¹²	1.6x10 ¹²	6.2	5.9	900	800
284	284 – F	222	0.01	2.5x10 ¹²	3.1x10 ¹¹	7.2	4.5	1100	1200
284	284 – G	222	0.1	2.5x10 ¹²	2.9x10 ¹¹	7.3	4.7	900	700

From the extracted parameters in Table 6.3, prediction of spectral responsivity for photodiode before and after UV exposure is performed based on 3D simulation of I-V photodiode responsivity. The internal quantum

deficiency – IQD responsivity is shown in Figure 6.6. For each exposure wavelength 222 nm, 279 nm and 300 nm, only the parameters of samples that were exposed with highest dose were chosen for spectral responsivity simulation. From simulation, slightly higher internal losses IQD observed after UV exposure.

Figure 6.6 Prediction of spectral responsivity of photodiode before and after UV exposure

7 Summary and Conclusions

The stability of chipS·CALe photodiodes against UV exposure have been studied *i)* directly by irradiating the photodiodes with UV light and *ii)* indirectly by irradiating test samples passivated identically to the photodiodes and predicting the change in response of the photodiodes with simulations based on the change in the lifetime and fixed charge density of test samples as a function of irradiation dose and energy. The irradiations were performed at wavelengths of 222 nm, 279 nm, 300 nm and 325 nm, and the dose was varied for each wavelength.

Irradiations at 300 nm and 325 nm were performed up to a dose of 100 J/cm² and no change in the responsivity of the photodiodes was observed. At irradiation wavelengths of 222 nm and 279 nm, on the other hand, the responsivity of the photodiodes started degrading at doses as low as 0,005 J/cm² and 0,6 J/cm², respectively. After obtaining these results from RISE and SFI Davos, PTB performed fine measurements for irradiation wavelengths 280 nm and 300 nm to verify the results with a higher accuracy. The spectral responsivity of the photodiodes in the wavelength range of 300 nm to 1005 nm did not change by more than 0.25 % when irradiated at a wavelength of 300 nm with an exposure of up to 100 J/cm² or at a wavelength of 280 nm with an exposure of up to 0.5 J/cm². The chipS·CALe photodiodes can therefore be considered stable in the 300 nm to 1005 nm wavelength range for many applications. The degradation of responsivity at irradiation wavelengths below 300 nm justifies the need for developing and fabricating more UV-radiation-hard photodiodes, which is addressed in the present project 22IEM06 S-CALe Up.

The simulations based on the measurements performed on test samples before and after UV irradiation predict the change in internal losses of the photodiodes due to irradiation to be slightly higher.

